

CONTEMPORARY METHODS OF LEARNING ENGLISH MORE EFFECTIVELY

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the consideration of various, in our opinion, effective ways of learning English. The publication examines the possibilities of using proprietary techniques that contribute to the rapid learning of foreign languages, and in particular English.

***Key words:** foreign language, educational system, vocabulary, communication, educational process, communication ability, motivation, level of knowledge*

Annotatsiya

Maqola turli xil, bizning fikrimizcha, ingliz tilini o'rganishning samarali usullarini ko'rib chiqishga bag'ishlangan. Nashr xorijiy tillarni, xususan, ingliz tilini tez o'rganishga hissa qo'shadigan xususiy texnikalardan foydalanish imkoniyatlarini o'rganadi.

***Kalit so'zlar:** chet tili, ta'lim tizimi, lug'at, muloqot, o'quv jarayoni, muloqot qobiliyati, motivatsiya, bilim darajasi.*

Аннотация

Статья посвящена обзору различных, на наш взгляд, эффективных методов изучения английского языка. В публикации исследуются возможности использования специальных методик, способствующих быстрому изучению иностранных языков, в частности, английского.

***Ключевые слова:** иностранный язык, система образования, словарный запас, общение, учебный процесс, коммуникативные способности, мотивация, уровень знания.*

INTRODUCTION

Currently, the labor market values high-level specialists with knowledge that is not limited to a narrow profile. One of the most important, and sometimes mandatory, areas of professional activity of a future graduate is the area of knowledge of a foreign language. Personnel who speak a foreign language, in particular English, have a greater chance of finding the coveted highly paid job than an applicant for the same vacancy who does not speak English.

Of course, each of us dreams of finding a decent, well-paid job in which we can effectively apply the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities not only in our specialty, but also in the field of knowledge and proficiency in a foreign language. Here you should understand the issue of choosing an effective way to learn English. One of the simplest, and, in our opinion, effective ways to master a foreign language is to master it with the help of a qualified mentor.

It is determined by the development of a set of additional exercises and assignments for the "English language" educational complex. Kuzovlev, this helps to increase the ability to communicate in foreign languages, and also increases and motivates children's interest in learning a foreign language „Salty science. – Arkhangelsk”

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

Teaching and learning English in the research process is popular methods, internet sources were used. During the writing of the article, the principles of theoretical deductive conclusion, analysis and synthesis, logicity were used.

The proposed research work on a foreign language “Modern effective ways of learning English” provides an examination of the methods of learning English by D. Khamidova, Dmitry Petrov, Ilya Frank In their works, they have demonstrated several English language methodologies that are easy to learn. According to d. Khamidova, “One of the most challenging parts of learning and teaching a foreign

language, for example, English as a second language, can be now considered correctly understanding the concept” [4,2021].

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

A friend of my mother’s sister or an acquaintance who once, somehow, taught somewhere, or speaks a little foreign language, does not seem to us an ideal option.

If you want to achieve an excellent and sustainable result, then it must be a highly qualified, qualified specialist who has proven his worth and has proven himself well. The ideal candidate, from our point of view, will be a teacher from a good school or university. You can always get an independent assessment (positive, neutral or negative) about him (or her) from his own students. Such a teacher is quite experienced and will be able to design an effective learning system for students. If the search for a competent specialist is successful, then sooner or later it will yield results and the student will achieve his goal. Often, in the process of learning a foreign language, students are faced with the problem of a lack of foreign vocabulary for more correct explanation.

Therefore, the problem of insufficient vocabulary needs to be addressed. However, resolving this issue can be quite problematic. Before saying something in a language foreign to the student, he first formulates a thought in his native means of communication. Very often it is quite problematic to translate this or that phrase into English, while maintaining the meaning and not making mistakes in the use of vocabulary. Currently, the labor market values high-level specialists with knowledge that is not limited to a narrow profile. One of the most important, and sometimes mandatory, areas of professional activity of a future graduate is the area of knowledge of a foreign language.

Personnel who speak a foreign language, in particular English, have a greater chance of finding the coveted highly paid job than an applicant for the same vacancy who does not speak English. Of course, each of us dreams of finding a decent, well-paid job in which we can effectively apply the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities not only in our specialty, but also in the field of knowledge and

proficiency in a foreign language. Here you should understand the issue of choosing an effective way to learn English. One of the simplest, and, in our opinion, effective ways to master a foreign language is to master it with the help of a qualified mentor. And here a lot depends on the teacher: when students study with a teacher, he bears a heavy burden of responsibility for the further success of his students. It is very important not to make a mistake and choose the right mentor. A friend of my mother's sister or an acquaintance who once, somehow, taught somewhere, or speaks a little foreign language, does not seem to us an ideal option. If you want to achieve an excellent and sustainable result, then it must be a highly qualified, qualified specialist who has proven his worth and has proven himself well. The ideal candidate, from our point of view, will be a teacher from a good school or university.

If the search for a competent specialist is successful, then sooner or later it will yield results and the student will achieve his goal. Often, in the process of learning a foreign language, students are faced with the problem of a lack of foreign vocabulary for more correct explanation. Therefore, the problem of insufficient vocabulary needs to be addressed. However, resolving this issue can be quite problematic. Before saying something in a language foreign to the student, he first formulates a thought in his native means of communication. Very often it is quite problematic to translate this or that phrase into English, while maintaining the meaning and not making mistakes in the use of vocabulary.

The solution to the above problem lies on the surface: you need to diversify your speech in every way: - reading books; - watching movies; - communication with a native speaker. On the one hand, the process of enriching vocabulary seems quite simple to us, but on the other hand it turns out to be very tedious, long and tedious. Therefore, the student should be patient. Choosing the right training system. Here it is worth deciding: how will the learning process be organized? Will it be organized by a teacher or foreign language tutor, or will the student organize it independently? In the first case, the entire burden of responsibility falls on the teacher, and in the second, on the person who has expressed a desire to learn

English. Here the student should engage in self-analysis and figure out what he has the most problems and difficulties with and focus on this in his training. If you have difficulties with speech (both written and oral), you should listen to more texts in a foreign language.

Problems with writing are solved by reading books and studying textbooks. The desire of the student himself is also important: without it, the learning process will not be successful. Motivation is something on which success in studying a discipline depends no less, and maybe even more, than anything else. This is what pushes each of us to take action to a greater extent. A motive is an impulse to action associated with satisfying the needs of a subject, and motivation is an incentive that activates the activity of a subject and determines the direction of this activity. Motivation is the most important component of teaching a foreign language at a university . The process of learning a foreign language is quite labor-intensive and requires time, effort and desire on the part of the student and professionalism on the part of the teacher. In most cases, when people study a foreign language, for example at school or university, they interact with only one teacher for a long time. As a result, one gets used to the pronunciation style of one person, which does not have the best effect on the communicative ability of students. When a person hears foreign speech from a direct native speaker, he gets lost and sometimes cannot understand the essence of the conversation. In such cases, you have to overcome difficulties in understanding foreign speech yourself. Of course, the more often you speak a foreign language, for example English, the faster you get rid of the audio barrier. As they say, “If you want to learn something, do it as often as possible” .

But today there are also alternative ways to overcome difficulties in perceiving foreign language speech. For example, many people listen to the radio, audio books in a foreign language, and also watch feature films with subtitles. According to many methodologists, one of the most effective ways is to watch podcasts on the Internet. Podcasts are either individual audio or video files, or a regularly updated series of files that can be downloaded from the Internet to a

computer or player. Podcasts produced by the BBC are very popular among foreign language learners .

When viewing video files, following the sentences, you see pictures on the screen that help you understand the content of the text. You can find podcasts on absolutely any interesting topic, for example, about history or traveling to a country whose language you are studying. Therefore, using podcasts not only develops your ability to master a foreign language, but also gives you the opportunity to learn a lot of new and useful information. An undoubted advantage of watching feature films is the abundance of dialogues, which allow you to get acquainted with all sorts of constructions and expressions often used in the colloquial speech of foreigners.

This method seems to us to be one of the most preferable and pleasant. In addition, subtitles help you translate a new phrase at any time, remember it and actively use it in your speech in prepared (for example, in class) and unprepared (in communication with foreigners) communication situations. You can also repeat the characters' lines out loud to improve your pronunciation. We become acquainted with music in early childhood, and it accompanies us throughout our lives. Songs help you relax, improve your mood and get a lot of positive emotions, which is, of course, very important when learning. According to numerous surveys, the majority of young people believe that listening to foreign language songs helps them get used to foreign speech and, moreover, expand their vocabulary and improve pronunciation. But to benefit from such listening, it is worth paying attention to the choice of music. In modern songs, too loud music often interrupts the words and is distracting.

Therefore, to begin with, it is better to choose slow solo compositions, and also first become familiar with the lyrics of the song. It is also worth noting that listening to various recordings is the most convenient way to improve the listening comprehension of foreign language speech, since recordings can be listened to at any convenient time: while doing household chores, while jogging, while traveling on the bus.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Learning to understand foreign spoken language is very difficult. Many people almost immediately give up what they started because they cannot translate most of the text into their native language. And this is not entirely the right approach to learning a foreign language. For example, all podcasts have different levels of complexity, which allows you to select the most appropriate text that matches the student's individual level of knowledge and foreign language proficiency.

Many experts note that in the first stages of using podcasts, the number of unfamiliar words should be about 45% of the total text. Therefore, if you want to get used to foreign language speech (in particular, to the version of speech in English), you should not think about every word of the text, but simply repeat after the speaker at his pace and intonation. In this case, at first, instead of the correct words, you may get only some hint of what should be ideally.

Of course, improving your English listening skills takes a lot of time, practice and effort. The most important thing is to remember that listening to foreign speech is not an innate gift or ability, but a skill that needs to be developed and constantly improved through regular training.

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